

THE ROLE OF ICT IN LEARNING AND TEACHING ENGLISH

Ag`zamova Muxlisa Muhammadiyevna

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute
English language and literature faculty student

O`ktamova Muxlisa

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute
English language and literature faculty student

Burkhanova Mamura Gulyamovna

Scientific advisor

ABSTRACT.

As 21st century is the globalization and developing age, we cannot imagine every field of our life without technology. Also education is not exception. Using technology in class and after class has become the most important part of the learning and teaching process. Teachers use them to adopt classroom activities and attract the students attention, thus increase language learning process. As Craig R.Barrett mention “With the help of technology teachers will be leaders in the transformation of education around the world”.

Key words: Teaching and learning, ICT, Apps, types of technologies.

Introduction. We have a lot of choice to choose from the world of technology in language teaching and learning. We can mention computers, TV, phone, language laboratory, Internet, e-mail, CD rom as the most effective ones. Moreover Mobile applications also give great advantage in the process of learning and teaching.

In the field of education the technological development open a new page, I mean today traditional methods of teaching are not giving good impact on the learners. Teaching with technology become the source of motivating students and a tool for motivating students to be innovative. This study focuses on the using new technologies in learning and teaching language and in this article I inform you about types of technologies, how to use them to improve language skills, advantages of technology and the effective of mobile apps in learning and teaching.

Literature analysis. Graddol (1997:16) said that “Technology lies at the heart of the globalization process affecting education, work and culture. The use of English

language has increased rapidly after 1960. At present the role and states of English language is that it is the language of social context, political, sociocultural business, education, library, communication across borders and key subject in curriculum and language of importing education” When technology enter to education the system of teaching changed dramatically, it means today's teachers are required to be aware of new technologies step by step.

As Bull and Ma stated (2001) “ technology provides, offers unlimited recourses to language learners” WE know computers as a main resource of technology and according to Becker (2000) computers are regarded as an important instructional instrument in language classes in which teachers have a convenient access are sufficiently prepared and have some freedom in the curriculum. Computer technology is regarded by a lot of teachers to be a significant part of providing a high quality education”. It is true that using computers in a class is a good way to teach effectively, give attention to students work in the same time, and check the assignments quickly. Jenifer Alemeng said that “Teaching in the internet age means we must teach tomorrow's skills today”.

As coin has two sides, we may face some drawbacks of using technologies on education. While pandemic period many bad websites. the most effective websites related to education are end mostly with .edu or .gov.

Moreover, Internet give the chance for people learn language not only at class but also at home which save time and energy without need of going somewhere, and any time they want.

Today we cannot imagine our life without mobile phones, which we can carry it all the time in our pocket or hand. It is little computer that can do every function of computer. In mobile phone helped language learning we can find protability, social interactivity, community, individuality and immediacy as S. Ammani and U. Aparanjan mentioned.

Information technology has given rise to various tools and applications which can be used by educational administration and teachers to track the progress of individual students and the parents can also be kept up to date about the achievement of their children, Even though, the mobile App development with IT has made education fun and exciting, The mobile apps can utilized in many ways in educating people, There are so many advantages of using mobile apps in our daily life. There are many advantages of Apps in language learning.

First of all it enhance classroom performance. learning through mobile apps like Seesaw helps students to improve their knowledge and to control aspects of their education. After class students can go through the lecture as many times they want and in this way they student can understand the theme fully without anybody's help.

Then they help to control time. Students do not waste their time with unnecessary activities, instead of it they can read e-books, listen recorded lectures or do home assignments.

It helps students to improve technological skills which is the demand of today's modern world. The more students work with apps, the more they will be good at technology world when they move on to the workplace.

Apps make learning fun. Sometimes reading the assignment, answering to questions, recording voice is boring, but with games it will be more interesting. Sometimes difficult tasks become more fun with games. For instance the top language learning apps help the students with new words and sentence formation by making any funny games. By introducing competitions and rewards motivate students to learn deeper the topic and Brilliant is might be an example for the best mobile app.

Apps is a good chance to learn individually. In a class with 30 or 40 student is taught for teacher, because it is impossible to give attention all the students in 40 minutes for teacher. By downloading the lesson to app open a way to learn individually to students.

It has benefits for nature and environment. You know we need lot of paper in study which is made from trees. And e-learning is friendlier way to learn without wasteful paper textbooks in favour of dynamic, frequently updated e-texts and use the online forms to submit homework rather than printed worksheets and essays.

To enter e-learning world can give an effort to reduce the use of paper and other fossil fuels.

The Role of ICT in 21st Century Teacher Education

ICT supports teachers in both in-service and in-service teacher training. ICT helps teachers interact with students. Help prepare lessons and provide feedback. It helps improve teaching skills and supports innovative teaching. Helps classroom effectiveness. It also helps enhance professional development and education. It improve active learning in management and teacher trainees. It now replaces old technology. As we know today, students will someday.

Always competitive. Therefore, teachers must have knowledge about them. This can be achieved through ICT. ICT helps teachers prepare for lessons.

Various methods and strategies are used in teacher training.

Various tools are used, such as word processors, databases, and spreadsheets. A variety of technology-based plans are used to assist teachers in their practice to teach. ICT enables teachers to use their skills in real-life classroom situations.

It can also create students for future occupations and social life. Using ICT as a "tool" to complete tasks, etc.

ICT is usually used regardless of subject. ICT as a medium for teaching and learning is a tool for teaching, Learning itself, the medium through which teachers teach and learners can to learn Appeared in various forms such as drills and exercises, In Simulation and Education Network. ICT as a general tool for organization and management in institutions. Teachers should provide technical support for learning on film.

Animation, simulation training that helped student teachers give models presentation When teachers have advanced technology, students

It also has technology. Eliminate traditional teaching methods and prepare teachers for application modern teaching ICT plays an important role in student assessment. ICT is the warehouse of educational institutions.

Information can be stored safely with ICT ICT helps teachers to communicate properly with their students so ICT bridge

Gap between teacher and student. ICT helps teachers convey information to students in the shortest possible time ICT helps teachers shape the educational environment ICT helps teachers identify creative children in educational institutions.

Discussion and conclusion. The main goal of using information technology in language learning and tachin is to promote students motivation and interests to learn languages, which can be practical way to lead them involved in the language learning

I believe that the use of new IT technologies will be further develop, and it makes teaching effectively and time consuming, and improve student learning possibility more and more in an easy way.

To sum up, the information related to this topic shows that technology provides interaction between teachers and students, helps them to improve all skills and be aware of latest news in education world

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